

LABORATORY EVALUATION OF FLAT FAN NOZZLE OF UAV SPRAYER

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Abstract

Pesticide application is an essential aspect of agriculture, contributing significantly to food security and economic stability. Nozzles play a crucial role in spraying, affecting the efficiency and effectiveness of pesticide applications. This study focused on the performance evaluation of a flat fan nozzle of a UAV sprayer using a patternator, which provides detailed insights into spray volumetric distribution and uniformity, key factors for precision agriculture. A flat fan nozzle was assessed at various heights (500 to 2500 mm) from the surface of the patternator and at pressures of 3, 5, 7 kg/cm². The optimal spray distribution was observed at a nozzle height of 2500 mm across all pressures, characterized by a high concentration of spray at the centre that gradually decreased towards the edges. The result shows that the working pressure increase from 3 to 7 kg/cm² leads to the average discharge rates increasing to 566.67 to 921.67 ml/min. The swath width increases from 920 to 2490 mm as the nozzle height increases from around 500 mm to 2500 mm and the pressure increases from 3 kg/cm² to 7 kg/cm². The nozzle height was increased from 500 to 2500 mm from the surface of the patternator, and the spray angle decreases from 103.12 to 51.46 degrees. The results indicate that higher nozzle pressure resulted in more uniform spray distribution. Specifically, the more uniform distribution was achieved at a nozzle height of 2500 mm and a pressure of 7 kg/cm². The insights gained from this research can guide the development of advanced nozzle technologies and best practice guidelines, supporting the broader adoption of UAV technology in precision agriculture.

Keywords – Sericulture, economic stability, patternator, UAV technology.

Introduction

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) or drones are modern machine used in agriculture for tasks like aerial spraying. Originally developed for military purposes, drones offer benefits such as increased efficiency, mobility, and the ability to cover large areas quickly, essential for disease and pest control, crop management, and optimizing agricultural inputs (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Precision agriculture in developed countries uses drones to collect data on yield, crop health, soil quality, and weather, helping farmers make informed decisions. The global agricultural drone services market is expected to grow significantly, providing opportunities for improved efficiency in farming.

In India, agriculture is a crucial sector of the economy, with a large proportion of the population engaged in farming. Issues like diseases, pests, and weeds lead to significant crop losses annually (Guo *et al.*, 2019). Chemical pesticides are commonly used but pose health risks to farmers. Agricultural drones equipped with sensors and cameras have been introduced to monitor crops, enhance farming operations, and increase yields. These drones offer flexibility, efficiency, and minimum crop damage, making them a suitable alternative for pesticide spraying and data collection. The use of pesticides and fertilizers in Indian agriculture is necessary for high productivity but also poses risks to human health. Over exposure to chemicals can lead to serious health issues such as cancer, respiratory problems, neurological disorders, asthma, allergies, hypersensitivity, and hormone disruptions (Weisenburger 1993). Neurological effects include memory loss, loss of coordination, slower response to stimuli, visual ability, mood swings, and changes in behaviour (Meivel *et al.*, 2016). To address these challenges, UAV technology has been introduced to reduce human labour and costs while improving economic returns. Drones provide precision, real-time data collection, and effective crop management, reducing human exposure to harmful chemicals during pesticide spraying.

The nozzle in a drone spraying system is essential to control the spray pattern, droplet size, and flow rate, ensuring consistent coverage, minimizing spray drift, and optimizing chemical application. Selecting the right nozzle enhances efficiency, accuracy, and environmental protection, thus improving the effectiveness of drone spraying. Keeping the above discussion in mind, the flat fan nozzle of UAV was evaluated on the horizontal patternator for effective drone spraying.

Material And Methods

The flat fan nozzle of UAV sprayer was evaluated in the laboratory of Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola for spray volumetric distribution, swath width, spray angle, and spray uniformity using horizontal patternator. The spray distribution pattern was observed on horizontal patternator

at varying height of nozzle and varying pressure from patternator surface.

The horizontal patternator was used to measure spray distribution and corrected spray patterns of flat fan nozzle of UAV. The frame of patternator was 2500 mm long, 1050 mm wide and height of 860 mm at the rear side and at the front to create a forward slope. It had 99 rectangular channels, each 65 mm high and 25 mm wide and glass tubes were set to collect spray liquid from each channel. The nozzle was centrally fixed and adjustable in height. When the nozzle sprays water an optimum operating pressure was maintained. A pressure gauge was mounted in pressurise water pipe line near the nozzle in horizontal patternator test rig. Pressure was set by using pressure control valve to a desire value. The height of the spray nozzle was adjusted by height adjustment arrangement. To ensure better spray volume distribution, parameters like swath width, operating pressure, height were standardized. Nozzles were tested at heights of 500 to 2500 mm from the patternator surface to simulate field conditions. The experiment was conducted at each combination of these variables, and observations were recorded. A flat fan nozzle was tested using a spray patternator. The nozzle was mounted on the patternator with its axis perpendicular to the horizontal plane. It was connected to a continuous water supply through a lance, a pressure gauge, and the pump outlet, with the pressure checked before starting. The pressure was set at 3, 5, and 7 kg/cm² for different heights using a pressure regulator. The nozzle assembly's height was adjusted by loosening a screw nut, moving the assembly to the desired height and then tightening the nut securely. Sprayed water was collected in measuring tubes, and the volume of liquid from each channel of the patternator was measured. This procedure was repeated thrice for each pressure and height settings.

Discharge rate

The discharge of a flat fan nozzle mounted on test rig was measured at 3, 5 and 7 kg/cm² pressure. The discharge rate was measured by collecting the discharged fluid (v) for a unit time of a minute (t) in a measuring cylinder and it was calculated as l/min.

$$Q = \frac{V}{t}$$

Where,

Q - Discharge rate (l/min)

V - Volume collected in the measuring tube (l)

t - Unit time to collect discharge (min)

Spray angle

The spray angle defined as the angle between the two outer edges of the spray pattern, measured at a specified distance from the nozzle. The height of the nozzles from the ground has to be adjusted with respect

to the height of plant canopy to get maximum coverage of spray (Pillai *et al.* 1999; Womac *et al.*, 1999; Watson and Wolff 1986). In agricultural applications, selecting the appropriate spray angle for nozzles are essential to achieve the desired coverage and efficiency, minimizing resource use while maximizing effectiveness. The spray angle for each nozzle was determined based on working width and nozzle height with in Indian Standard IS: 8548-77. The spray angle of the nozzle was calculated using the formula.

$$W = 2h \tan \frac{\theta}{2}$$

Where,

W - Spray width (mm)

h - Spray height (mm)

θ - Spray angle (degree)

Uniformity coefficient of spray

A patternator was used to test the nozzles' spray uniformity. The nozzle was tested under various pressure and height conditions. The coefficient of variation (CV) was used to determine spray uniformity. Coefficient of variation is the measure of variability of the data. When the value of coefficient of variation is higher, it means that the data has high variability and less stability. When the value of coefficient of variation is lower, it means the data has less variability and high stability. The formula was used to compute the coefficient of variation.

$$CV = \frac{SD}{\bar{a}} \times 100 \quad \bar{a} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_i}{n} \quad SD = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(a_i - \bar{a})^2}{[n-1]}}$$

Where,

CV - Coefficient of variation (%)

a_i - Volume collected in each measuring tube (ml)

Table 1. Average discharge rate of flat fan nozzle

R₁, R₂, R₃ Replications

Pressure, kg/cm ²	Discharge rate, ml/min			
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Average
3	520	580	600	566.67
5	750	740	710	733.33
7	925	960	880	921.67

Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on spray angle of flat fan nozzle

The effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on spray angle of flat fan nozzle shown in the Fig. 4. The maximum spray angle 103.12 degree obtained at nozzle height 500 mm and operating pressure of 7 kg/cm², and the minimum spray angle 51.46 degree was observed at nozzle height 2500 and operating pressure of 3 kg/cm². Increasing the operating pressures from 3 to 5 kg/cm² increased the spray angle, resulting in a more extensive coverage area. Actual spray angle decreases with an increase of nozzle height because of the effect of gravity. This effect is most pronounced for the finer sprays (Minov *et al.*, 2014).

The result shown Fig. 4 the nozzle height increasing from 500 to 2500 mm and spray angle decrease from 103.12 to 51.46 degrees. The results are similarly accordance to the results stated by Padhee *et al.*, (2019).

Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on swath width of flat fan nozzle

Swath width of the flat fan nozzle shown graphically in the Fig. 5. The increasing nozzle height resulted in a broader swath width but lower peak discharge values. This trend suggests that higher nozzle heights are beneficial for applications requiring uniform coverage over large areas.

Higher operating pressures enhance the spray's reach and uniformity, resulting in broader swath widths and increased volumetric discharge. The maximum swath width by a observed nozzle was 2490 mm at

n - Number of measuring tubes used in the experiment

\bar{a} - Average spray volume collected across all measuring tube (ml)

Results And Discussion

The effect of heights of nozzle from the surface of patternator and operating pressures of nozzle on spray volumetric distribution, discharge rate and spray angle were studied.

Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on spray volumetric distribution

The spray volumetric distribution of flat fan nozzle on horizontal patternator at varying pressure and height are shown in Figs. 1 to 3. Increasing the nozzle height from surface of patternator results in flatter and wider distribution curves, indicating a broader swath but lower peak discharge values. (Kailashkumar *et al.*, 2022) reported the same trend in their study.

Also reported was the same trend in their study. This trend is beneficial for applications that require uniform coverage over large areas. Higher operating pressures enhance the spray's reach and uniformity, resulting in broader swath widths and increased volumetric discharge. The volumetric spray distribution was observed more uniform at a nozzle height of 2500 mm at all the three operating pressure of nozzle.

Effect of working pressure on discharge rate

Higher working pressures generally result in higher discharge rates, improving the flow of liquid through the nozzles. The working pressure increases from 3 to 7 kg/cm² leads to the average discharge rates are 566.67, 733.33, 921.67 ml/min respectively (Table 1). The results indicate that working pressure affect the discharge rate. The discharge rate of nozzle increasing with pressure, which is similar with the findings stated by Sridhar and Asokan (2019).

nozzle height 2500 mm and at an operating pressure of 7 kg/cm² and smallest swath width was observed 920 mm at 500 nozzle height and at operating pressure of 5 kg/cm².

Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on uniformity coefficient of spray

Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on uniformity coefficient of spray, shown in Table 2. The coefficient of variation (CV) results shows that operating pressure, and nozzle height significantly affect spray uniformity distribution. Increasing operating pressure tends to reduce the coefficient of variation of the spray, leading to more uniform spray distribution (Hassen *et al.*, 2013). The flat fan nozzle gives most uniform distribution with a coefficient of variation 25.23 % at height 2500 mm and operating pressure 7 kg/cm² (Padhee *et al.*, 2019).

Statistical analysis of experimental data

The data generated through the experiment of flat fan nozzle on horizontal patternator was statistically analysed. The optimal custom design was used to analysed the data in Design Expert software and shown in Table 3. The R² value calculated by least square technique and found to be 0.99, showing good fit of model to the data. The model F values 428.66, 49.38 and 88.95 is of spray angle, swath width and uniformity coefficient implies that the model is significant (p<0.01). It is also clearly seen from the Table 3 that nozzle height is the most prominent factor which has a effect on spray angle, swath width and uniformity coefficient followed by nozzle pressure.

Table 2. Coefficient of variation of flat fan nozzle

Sr. No	Nozzle height from patternator, mm	Coefficient of variation, %		
		3 kg/cm ²	5 kg/cm ²	7 kg/cm ²
1	500	77.68	73.14	70.31
2	750	69.01	65.85	74.99
3	1000	65.98	52.25	47.89
4	1250	65.68	48.31	36.23
5	1500	53.77	31.97	36.19
6	1750	46.78	41.26	41.2
7	2000	33.22	27.82	34.51
8	2250	34.23	38.82	41.28
9	2500	29.83	29.21	25.23

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Table 3. ANOVA for independent parameters on performance parameters

	Spray angle, degree	Swath width, mm	Uniformity coefficient of spray, %
Model	428.66	49.38	88.95
A-Nozzle height	1857.69	211.79	427.87
B-Pressure	7.58	1.38	22.88
AB	3.56	0.2421	4.41
A ²	121.32	16.75	5.20
B ²	1.14	4.27	0.7428
Lack of Fit	3.44	4.63	4.42
Mean	70.86	1851.25	48.16
Standard Deviation	1.45	114.49	2.79
Coefficient of variation, %	2.04	6.18	5.79
R ²	0.9954	0.9611	0.9780

R²- Regression coefficient

Significant at 1% level

Conclusions

The increase the nozzle height from 500 mm to 2500 mm results in flatter and wider distribution curves, which is beneficial for applications to uniform coverage over large areas. Higher operating pressures, from 3 to 7 kg/cm², improve the spray's reach and uniformity, leading to broader swath widths and higher volumetric discharge rates. The optimal spray distribution was observed at a nozzle height of 2500 mm across all operating pressures. Distribution patterns showed a high concentration of spray at the centre, decreasing towards the edges, necessitating precise calibration for effective application.

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Fig. 1 Spray volumetric distribution of flat fan nozzle at 3 kg/cm² operating pressure and at different heights

Fig. 2 Spray volumetric distribution of flat fan nozzle at 5 kg/cm² operating pressure and at different heights

Fig. 3 Spray volumetric distribution of flat fan nozzle at 7 kg/cm² operating pressure and at different heights

Fig. 4 Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on spray angle of flat fan nozzle

Fig. 5 Effect of nozzle height and operating pressure on swath width of flat fan nozzle